

**Road Rage or Road Cage: A Study of the Ecological Impacts of Roads on
Wildlife Corridors and the Resultant Habitat Fragmentation**

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INTRODUCTION

“The effect of roads on wild animal populations are one of the most pressing contemporary conservation issues and with road networks increasing globally we need to urgently address this” (Rogers, 2023, par. 23). Road-killed animals are victims of the transportation infrastructure boom, a global crisis that is affecting wildlife and habitats around the world (Bryner, 2018; Forman, et al, 2003; “How Likely Are You”, 2023; etc.). In the United States, an estimated 10 million animals and 40 thousand people are killed by wildlife vehicle collisions (WVCs) each year. The number of these collisions has increased in the last 15 years by 50%, with the average American having a 1 in 127 chance of having a collision with an animal (Bryner, 2018; Hardy, Amanda, et al, 2003). In Louisiana, Interstate 10, specifically the 15-mile stretch between Sorrento and LaPlace, bisects a natural swamp and wooded habitat with no safe corridors for the wildlife that inhabits this large region. This stretch encompasses part of the Maurepas Swamp Wildlife Management Area, one of the largest forested wetlands in the United States that creates habitat for a variety of animals ranging from alligators to deer to bald eagles. Parallel to the results of the I-10 construction in Louisiana, urbanization causes a disruption in ecological connectivity resulting in habitat fragmentation. This fragmentation affects wildlife corridors that are used for migrations, mating, feeding, and other vital activities crucial to an animal’s survival. Without ecological connectivity and wildlife corridors, territories are limited, mating and feeding grounds are decreased, and genetic diversity is reduced. One species significantly affected by this issue in Louisiana is the American alligator. Louisiana culture is defined by many aspects, including but not limited to food, music, community, and the swampy marshlands that make up the majority of the state’s coast. This study will focus on the negative impacts that habitat fragmentation has on the animal species located within the Maurepas Swamp region, namely the American alligator. The process of study will include roadkill inventories, mappings and summarizations of the data, site selection, conceptual studies, and the development of a wildlife crossing structure. These steps will create a design process that can be repeated in other areas

across the world to reconnect ecological corridors and restore fragmented habitats. This study is significant to Louisiana in its goal to restore the swamp and wetlands that support and define Louisiana's unique culture and community.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

The goal of this study is to provide a clear understanding of the direct impacts of roadway construction on natural habitats, specifically that habitat found between Sorrento and LaPlace, Louisiana. More specifically, this study aims to:

- Describe how habitats and animal species are disrupted and negatively affected by roadways.
- Analyze the statistics of WVCs along Interstate 10 in Louisiana.
- Provide a clear understanding of the ecological corridors in this region and develop designs to re-establish these corridors and reduce WVCs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

ROAD ECOLOGY

The term “road ecology,” coined by Richard Forman in 1993, is “defined loosely as the study of how ‘life change[s] for plants and animals with a road and traffic nearby’” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 6). This term became a way for researchers, scientists, and engineers alike to view the human world and its infrastructure through the eyes of nonhumans. This way of thinking informs design and is more effective at creating designs that are more inclusive. It answers such questions as: “How does a moose comprehend traffic? What sort of tunnel appeals to a mink? Why do grizzly bears prefer crossing over highways while black bears go under?” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 9). Roads are numerous and exhaustive. They comprise such an expansive network that they must now be reconsidered. It is time to reevaluate and ask, are all roads necessary? “*Why [does this] road cross [this] land?*” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 10). Just as animals have adapted to living in a human-dominated world, we as humans must adapt to live with animals. This concept has been known by researchers as “anthropogenic resistance” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 85). Geographer Jennifer Wolch is spreading awareness

about doing just that. Wolch has described a phenomenon that occurs when humans and wildlife coexist: zoöpolis. At the heart of this notion is “interspecies empathy: when you share a city with wildlife, you can’t help but ‘grasp animal standpoints or ways of being’” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 86).

In the United States, pavement takes up less than one percent of land coverage. However, the “road effect zone,” the area of natural systems that are affected by roads and highways, is a total of 20 percent of land coverage. Jochen Jaeger, a German road ecologist, made the term “landschaftszer-schneidung” known. Translated as “landscape dissection,” it is like fragmentation but differs in the way the dissection occurs. Fragmentation “can be inflicted by all manner of forces – deforestation, farming, development – [while] dissection connotes the surgical precision of a road slicing through land” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 65). In the United States, this dissection has resulted in islands that support species that have essentially been barricaded by the roads, leading to a reduction in the genetic diversity found within these parcels. Research has found that some smaller animals may cross over into other islands through gutters or drainage pipes, but they seldom reproduce, further hindering the gene pool. Additionally, human growth and continued urbanization result in habitat loss while the roads designed to create human connectivity result in wildlife mortality.

The effects of roads are numerous and wide-ranging. Roads have been documented to affect animal herd sizes and diversity, contribute to greenhouse gas emissions, disfigure landscapes, accelerate habitat loss, and much more. Fifty years ago, only 3 percent of land-dwelling mammals died on roads. By 2017 that number had quadrupled. Roads have an equally negative effect on flora as well. In the Amazon, roads that were built through the damp, dark rainforests brought in heat, light, and exposure that forced trees to drop “leaves to conserve water” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 262). Such a phenomenon is known as “edge effects” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 262). It should be noted, however, that roadsides sometimes create new ecosystems. In Britain, butterflies feed on milkweed that has grown in the medians and roadside ditches; these such ecosystems are known as “soft estates” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 5). Roads are not only dangerous to wildlife but also to human users.

Forty thousand Americans die each year on the road, more than 100 people a day. The attitude towards that number varies from person to person, but, as Barry Lopez has put it, these deaths are sometimes viewed as “Horrible, unavoidable, justified” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 10). However justified some people might view these casualties, it is important to note that almost \$200 billion is spent on roads in the US annually, mostly for repairs rather than new construction. This expense could be reduced if the number of roads was reduced.

Additionally, roads affect humans as well. Around 3,600 people across the world die every day from car-related incidents. Furthermore, people are affected in ways that they might not even realize:

The same engine noise that chases off birds ramps up our own cortisol production. The same pavement that sweeps motor oil into Puget Sound absorbs and discharges solar radiation, forming urban heat islands that make hot summers deadly. The same salt that’s turning midwestern lakes into estuaries corroded pipes in Flint, Michigan, and released lead into its water supply. The same traffic that cleaves bobcat populations contributes to our social isolation; the same freeways that thwart Los Angeles’s cougars make road-raging commuters more prone to committing domestic violence. (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 274)

Road Ecologist William Laurance has acknowledged that instead of being development averse, an effort needs to be made to develop responsibly. This includes “clustering roads together rather than letting them sprawl,” and improving existing roads rather than building new ones (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 269). Essentially, roads should be planned and the “economic benefits and ecological costs [should] be weighed and balanced” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 270). In Brazil, a state highway known as SP-139 exemplifies the notion that wildlife does not always abide by the rules of a road but rather it is the opposite. This highway is closed to all traffic other than emergency vehicles between the hours of 8:00 PM and 6:00 AM and the road itself is designed to slow its drivers and force them to adhere to the speed limit listed.

ROAD INFRASTRUCTURE WITHIN THE UNITED STATES

Roads and infrastructure are so abundant that, in some cases, they shape the evolution of species. Roads take up almost 40 million miles and could encircle the earth 1,606 times. There is “three thousand tons of infrastructure for every human, nearly a third of an Eiffel tower per person” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 3). These numbers are impactful alone, but paired with the adverse effects they produce, they are astonishing.

When road numbers started to increase, the technology used to build them advanced. Dirt and gravel roads were paved, and these paved surface roads allowed for greater speeds. This increase in speed also increased the roadkill rate. A connection was formed: “The better the road, the bloodier” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 23). The Good Roads Revolution, a movement that started in the 1870s and gained traction in the early 1920s with the car boom, called for better and improved roads on which vehicles and bicycles could ride. This movement “transformed cars into superpredators—heavy, impervious, impossibly fast” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 25). Wildlife facing a car does not stand a chance. The creation and implementation of jersey barriers protect cars and drivers driving in opposite directions but trap animals that make it onto the road. Roadkill is often unnoticed and is therefore not considered a problem by many. Some people go as far as to blame roadkill victims. With time and increased traffic flow, “roadkill could indeed diminish a population, even extirpate it” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 95). A key aspect to note about roadkill is that the significance of the impact is not measured in the number of animals killed but instead in which specific ones are being killed. Natural selection ensures that the strongest, most viable species survive and reproduce so that the weaker genetic lines eventually die off altogether. Roadkill, however, “eliminate[s] the strong [as well] as the feeble” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 95).

Within the United States specifically, there are four million miles of road with only “a couple thousand dedicated wildlife crossings” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 207). The United States Forest Service, a federal agency, manages 193 million square miles of land in America. Within its purview specifically lie 370,000 miles of roads, built mostly for the logging industry. These roads are as disruptive as they are numerous. While many of these roads are in use today, many more are not but have not been removed and the land returned to its natural state.

When the Wilderness Act was passed in 1964, wilderness itself was defined with the hope to return some areas to the wild but also to preserve existing expanses of wild land. This Act declared that “any roadless block of public land that measured at least five thousand contiguous acre” must be protected (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 122). Following in these footsteps, an engineer who worked for the Forest Service, Anne Connor, had the goal of having several out-of-service agency roads decommissioned, and, by 2005, “more than five hundred road miles had been expunged” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 127). These roads, once the spur of economic development within rural communities but were now ghosts of the past, were once again providing jobs and opportunities for the rural communities which they served. Road decommissioning created jobs just as road construction had. Scientists have calculated that “decommissioning just 1 percent of Forest Service roads each year ... would increase wildlife habitat by around 25 percent” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 132).

ECOLOGICAL AND WILDLIFE CORRIDORS

At its core, an ecological corridor is simply a continuous, uninterrupted connection across an area or a landscape. These corridors act as natural pathways through which organisms such as plants and animals can move or disperse from one place to another as needed. Animal movements vary by species and can range anywhere from daily foraging routes to annual migrations to once-in-a-lifetime dispersal events (“What Is Ecological Connectivity”, 2023). Ecological corridors also serve to promote both structural and functional connectivity. While functional connectivity is organism-oriented and relates to habitat connection from an organism’s point of view, structural connectivity is related to the landscape and what barriers might exist that interfere with the connectivity of the landscape (LaPoint, Scott, et al, 2015). Such corridors are of vital importance due to the genetic diversity found within them which in turn supports population stabilization. These corridors are often identified by their terrain and any special features “that indicate optimal paths of movement, including topography, elevation, vegetation type, or physical barriers like roads or rivers that might direct wildlife movement” (Shor, 2022, par. 4). Similar to ecological corridors are wildlife corridors. The movement routes of wildlife to complete their life cycles are called wildlife corridors and can “span anywhere from a

stretch of river to a whole continent” (Morse, 2021, par. 1). Wildlife refuges serve to fill in the gaps and overcome the obstacles created by the construction of roads and infrastructure. However, the more miles an animal travels, the more obstacles they encounter. To combat this, these refuges sometimes partner with private landowners to create continuous pathways across “the mosaic of public and private lands” (Morse, 2021, par. 6). Government funding can serve as an incentive for local landowners to open their land to wildlife. For example, The Department of the Interior granted \$2.1 million in 2019 to state and local partners in “several Western States to conserve habitat corridors for elk, mule deer and pronghorn” (Morse, 2021, par. 7). Creating and improving migration corridors can also serve local wildlife communities through plantings of native fauna that provide food and shelter as well as the removal of invasive species that can threaten the natives. Corridors also exist for smaller creatures such as insects and other pollinators. Monarch butterflies migrate around 3,000 miles from Mexico and California to their northern breeding grounds. Small improvements such as planting butterfly or native pollinator gardens in residential yards, school campuses, libraries, etc., can serve as rest stops as butterflies and pollinators complete their migrations.

HABITAT FRAGMENTATION

The result of a disruption in ecological corridors that breaks the connectivity of the landscape is called habitat fragmentation. These small, disconnected patches of habitat are isolated from each other, which has a range of effects from degraded surface water to decreases in the number and variety of species found within each patch. These isolated patches of habitat often have: a lack of genetic diversity due to inbreeding, resulting in weak or potentially sterile offspring; loss of migration corridors; biological impacts such as a change in the natural communities, i.e., plant palette, of a specific patch. Many organisms are multi-habitat, meaning that they move from one habitat to another throughout the day to survive. These organisms often die out in or leave areas that no longer have the proper connections to support them (Forman, et al, 2003). Alligators are no exception. It should also be noted that when many different habitats or land types cross in areas with roadways cut through them, there is a higher risk for a WVC due to the higher

number of animals moving within the landscape. However, some studies have proven that wildlife crossings with a diverse planting palette and design reduce this risk.

EFFECTS ON ANIMALS AND THEIR BEHAVIOR

It was estimated that one year of reduced travel in a select number of states who collect and analyze carcass cleanup statistics “would save twenty-seven thousand large animals in those states alone” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 291). In addition to causing wildlife deaths, cars and vehicles on roads pollute and destroy habitats through water runoff, wrecks, explosions, and so on. Pollutants such as “copper from brake linings, zinc from tire wear, nitrogen oxides from exhaust, cadmium from paint, residual lead from leaded gasoline, [and] microplastics from everything” run off the road during rainstorms and end up in roadside ecosystems (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 169).

While some animals are known as sentinel species, roadkill can be considered a “sentinel phenomenon, a process that reveals transitions over time” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 240). A major mal effect of the road system on wildlife, among others, is the disruption to daily ranges and migration corridors. Roads bisect once continuous habitats and act as barriers to those who use the habitats to complete their migratory routes. They face death by vehicle collisions or starvation. Starvation occurs when the herd takes longer to cross roads or freeways and thus does not make it to their final destination before the weather kills off their food sources. Some animal migration routes are passed down through generations similar to the way oral histories are passed down in indigenous tribes. Does pass down these routes to their fawns, but when a road prevents their crossing, “the loss is as thorough as the erasure of a language” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 40). Migration is an essential movement that many species need to complete in order to survive. If roads and traffic prevent such movement, the results will be fatal; “Animal lives are defined by mobility” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 40). The survival of migrations is dependent on an animal’s vagility, the ability to move freely and migrate. Infrastructure and roads act as impasses that affect such needs. According to biologist Sandra Jacobson, animals can be placed into four categories that are based on their reactions to roads: nonresponders, pausers, avoiders,

and speeders. Nonresponders are those who ignore the dangers of the road and are most often hit; pausers will walk onto the road but then stop and huddle when facing oncoming traffic; avoiders generally abstain from approaching or using all roads; and speeders are those who speed across roads and leave their lives up to fate. Humans are typically considered speeders. When traffic is light, streets and roads feel safer to cross. The same thought process was observed in animal speeders, and the concept of gap acceptance was attributed to animals as well as people. Gap acceptance is a term coined by a pedestrian study that essentially proved a person was more likely to cross a road when there was little to no traffic. With this idea in mind, ecologist Corinna Riginos observed deer along a highway and studied their habits. She found that if cars were going by with 30 seconds or less in between each one, deer were less likely to cross and more likely to be hit. If the gap in cars was more than a minute, deer crossed usually without casualties. The gaps that were in between these two were considered “gray areas, sometimes perilous, sometimes not” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 49). There are many components that influence WVC occurrences other than animal reaction types, including but not limited to traffic characteristics such as rush hours or higher speed limits, land use, and road infrastructure.

In 1969, Idaho opened Interstate 84 that ran through a deer migration corridor. When the deer began their journey, they were stopped by this new road. The state released rations to sustain the deer that were congregating in the roadsides as the season brought snow, but “hundreds starved, and a herd once two thousand animals strong crashed to eight hundred gaunt survivors” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 43). Two years later in the winter of 1971 in Wyoming, a wildlife fence prevented a herd of pronghorn from crossing Interstate 80 and more than three thousand members of the herd died. The interstate was less than a hundred feet wide, “yet [it] had inflicted massive habitat loss, denying animals access to millions of acres of life-sustaining land” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 43). While some of these examples highlight known migrations, there are plenty of animal migrations that are still unknown and therefore the damage done by roads cannot be known.

The effects of roads and urbanization on rare species tend to get more notice than those on abundant populations. The thought process being that rare species have a harder time

surviving and reproducing since their populations are already so small and threatened than those species which are more abundant. However, abundant ones are now losing so many numbers that they too are threatened. In the United States, “at least twenty-one critters are existentially threatened by cars” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 92). In the world, about 60% of animal populations have declined since 1970 and one third of the population since 1900. Reptiles and amphibians, collectively known as “herps,” are an example of a once abundant animal population now reduced to fragments. Herp populations generally diminish in localized areas rather than all at once, so the effect is not immediately noticed. This occurrence, known as extirpations, consists of “many small losses that over time can amount to a very big one” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 93).

It is not easy to readily understand the effects of roadkill on wildlife populations because it takes time for them to manifest. Extinction is understood because it is something that has already happened. The road to extinction is much harder to see. There are a few different terms used by researchers to describe this event, “*defaunation...biological annihilation...Eremocene*,” but they all mean essentially the same thing: an “age of loneliness, a near and desolate future in which humankind bestrides an empty world, or perhaps drives over it” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 96).

Another obstacle impeding the understanding of roadkill effects is the frequency with which roadkill is removed from roads. Personnel at the federal, state, county, and private levels are hired, and rarely is a record kept of the slain animals. These workers drag the roadkill off the road and leave them some 10-15 feet in the fringe habitat that exists past the shoulder, take them to landfills, or donate the carcasses to vets or animal shelters. When roadkill inventories are performed, the data is not always accurate because some of the roadkill may have been removed before it could be catalogued.

Roads can affect animal mortality rates in more ways than just roadkill. Noise pollution is a serious problem and can lead to infertility, stress, and in extreme cases, death, among animal species. In the United States, “more than 80 percent of the [country] lies within a kilometer of a road, a distance at which cars project twenty decibels and trucks and

motorcycles around forty” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 134). Not only does noise pollution affect wildlife but people as well. It can affect sleeping habits, brain function, and stress levels that can lead to health problems such as “high blood pressure, diabetes, heart attacks, and strokes” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 135). A study was conducted in France that measured noise effects on human life spans and found that it “shortens the average Parisian life span by ten months. In the loudest neighborhoods, it truncates lives by more than *three years*” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 135). In Wyoming, the Devils Tower National Monument landscape is home to prairie dogs, bats, deer and more. This site is also the location of a motorcycle rally. It has been found that the noise pollution from the nearby rally “pushes prairie dogs back into their burrows, drives off deer, and deters bats from feeding near the monument for weeks” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 135). It is important to note the difference between sound and noise. Sound is something natural like wind or animal noises whereas noise is something manmade like the pop of a car backfiring. Noise pollution, in any form, can have significant effects. Increases in background noise, even by just 3 decibels, “ halves the ‘listening area,’ the space in which an animal can pick up a signal” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 141). This effect can also have negative impacts on “the ecological processes they catalyze, among them seed dispersal, pollination, and pest control” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 141).

Animal-rights activists generally tend to focus “on ‘negative rights,’ like the right to not be killed, tortured or confined,” but some scholars believe that there should be a shift in how we view animals and their rights (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 216). These people believe that society should instead focus on how we can act on an animal’s behalf through better designing our buildings, roads, and neighborhoods. Research shows that WVCs are the leading human cause of wildlife fatalities, with the number of accidents increasing by around 50% in the past 15 years. Studies have been conducted to estimate the effectiveness that fences, wildlife bridges, and tunnels have on preventing these collisions and have found these additions to be 90% effective (Bryner, 2018). Various data collection techniques highlighted in the research are as follows:

- Accident reports by police or hunters.
- Road surveys by ecologists or volunteers.

- Sensor-driven approaches.

LOCATING AND RECORDING ROADKILL

In some cases, roadkill rates can be the leading factor in determining population size, sometimes exceeding natural causes such as predation or disease. However, roadkill data is not always accurate because it does not always consist of every victim, and it requires large numbers of people to gather it. Many systems and methods have been devised to streamline this data collection, and a very common one is to “[enlist] the public’s help” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 234). There are two different types of personnel used for recording data: experts and volunteers or bystanders. Experts are considered to be practicing wildlife ecologists and employees in natural protection areas. There is no completely accurate method for measuring WVCs, so persistence, entry probability, and the probability of detecting a carcass need to be quantified to reduce bias when conducting surveys. In addition, there have not been enough large-scale studies conducted to determine which measures are most effective in WVC reduction, but measures such as warning signs, fences, and reflectors are not considered to be effective interventions (Pagany, 2020). Around 1960, the Humane Society in the United States recruited road-trippers to count roadkill every Fourth of July. These surveys gave “a rough estimate of daily American roadkill that’s still commonly quoted: one million vertebrate animals struck each day” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 234). With the age of technology and smartphones came applications that allow users to record roadkill sightings. The traffic and map application Waze added a roadkill button and in Israel “drivers reported twelve thousand animals within six months” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 235). A Welsh student came up with Project Splatter, an awareness project that “encouraged the public to tweet their sightings” to the application formerly known as Twitter, now X (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 235). Another such program is a nonprofit based out of Montana known as Adventure Scientists. This organization recruits outdoorspeople to gather data while they are out on personal trips and excursions. As this data is reviewed, hot spots were identified along stretches of roads where collisions were happening in higher volumes and frequencies. However, it was also discovered that greater numbers of collisions were happening at specific times. These hot moments can

“last a season ... or a single evening” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 237). Researchers have calculated that “enacting permanent DST ... would prevent enough nighttime driving to spare the lives of thirty-three drivers and some thirty-six thousand deer every year” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 237).

At the core of the data problem is the lack of consistency between states and jurisdictions. Each transportation agency “has a different process for quantifying the carcasses that its personnel scrape off the pavement” and there is no singular database from which data can be pulled and analyzed (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 238).

As autonomous vehicles (AVs) continue to gain popularity, researchers and ecologists are discussing the opportunities that they create when it comes to roadkill cataloguing. In the mid-2010s in Portugal, a “research team began developing an automated roadkill mapping system” that consisted of “sleek, bumper-mounted laser cameras and a laptop running a roadkill-identification algorithm” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 245). This is one example of how AVs can be used to identify and map roadkill and provide more information on this problem.

CROSSING STRUCTURE EXAMPLES

Many methods have been developed to help alleviate animal casualties but not all of them have been deemed effective. An easy solution to this problem seemed to be putting up signage depicting animal crosses. However, signage along roads became so ubiquitous that motorists were no longer noticing them or were choosing to ignore them. This strategy was cheap and convenient but not an actual solution to the problem (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 32). On the other hand, animal detection systems have been found to reduce animal collisions by about 50 percent. These systems are electrical signs that “only light up when there’s actually an animal to detect and thus prevent driver habituation” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 297). Another such strategy was reflectors along roadsides intended to scare off wildlife. This strategy was also found to be ineffective and only reduced collisions by 1 percent. One method that has proven to be effective, with some caveats, is wildlife fencing along roadways. One such fence in Minnesota was found to reduce deer-vehicle collisions by more than 90 percent. Some drawbacks of this method include poor construction of the

fence and abrupt endings that allow animals to simply follow the fence line until it ends and then gain access to the road at such endings. The actual road traffic itself is not necessarily a developed method but rather a barrier. When traffic is congested and fast enough, it can act as an almost solid wall and prevent animals from crossing the road. Road ecologists have found that “roads with more than 10,000 vehicles per day should be considered absolute barriers to most wildlife” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 50).

When creating crossing structures, the most common mistake is designing for cost efficiency, not usage efficiency. Engineers who design crossing structures are oftentimes designing them to support more than one purpose, and this results in a sterile and uninviting crossing that seems foreign to wildlife which results in a lack of usage. Engineers in Wyoming designed culverts for deer to go under Interstate 80 that “measured ten feet wide, ten feet high, and several hundred feet long” that the deer rejected. The deer instead found holes in the fencing that was built to guide them to the culverts or simply walked to end of the fence line and entered the road at those points. It wasn’t until a man named Hank Henry lined the culverts with food and hay that the deer started to use them. However, the continuous lining of the culverts with food and hay was unsustainable, and so Henry and his supervisor Lorin Ward persuaded the highway administration to extend the fence line. At the new end of the line was a dirt underpass intended for machinery crossings. However, this underpass felt more natural and blended with the landscape and was thus more appealing to the deer than the concrete culverts. This addition resulted in high deer usage of the crossing and a decline in roadkill by nearly 90%. It was concluded that fences “kept ungulates off the interstate. Underpasses got them across it” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 52).

When constructing a crossing structure, it is vital to find ways to encourage wildlife usage. The effectiveness of an underpass, as engineer John Eddins found, was due to what he considered an openness ratio. This ratio could be determined by multiplying width by height and dividing by length. A tunnel’s openness was the key to maximizing its usage and effectiveness. However, it should be noted that research has not found a link between an increase in genetic diversity and wildlife overpasses. When determining the most

appropriate location for a crossing structure, mapping out roadkill is one method. However, this method is not always appropriate, especially not in places where roadkill is too prolific. An alternative method is looking at places that essentially make the most sense. These are places where the natural land seems to converge with another with the only barricade being a man-made road.

As popularity for such preventative measures increased and more were implemented, a formula for success was soon established. Crossings should be no more than a mile apart, fences should stretch a minimum of 3 miles, and “jump-outs”, ramps that allow deer to escape if they break through the fences, were to be placed strategically. This formula can be customized to fit specific locations and functions through additions such as skylights or the removal of hanging ledges from which predators might be able to hide.

Cost per collision is necessary when gathering funding for wildlife crossings. A group of road ecologists led by Marcel Huijser determined the average cost per collision based on “hospital bills, the car repairs, the loss to hunters, and so on” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 54). On average, deer collisions cost \$6,600, elk cost \$17,500, and moose cost \$31,000 (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 54). With these calculations, underpasses and wildlife fencing could save the public money. In Wyoming, the Nugget Canyon underpasses prevented “ninety-five crashes annually, [paying] for themselves within 5 years” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 55). In the United States, most funding for such projects comes from state and federal transportation budgets because of such cost-saving analyses. Some projects, such as the overpass at Liberty Canyon that stretches across US 101, are funded through private donations. This funding is much harder to come by and requires much more advertising and promoting.

With only twelve wildlife overpasses, the United States is trailing behind Germany, Switzerland, Austria, and the Netherlands. These countries’ overpasses are also known as “ecoducts, green bridges, and landscape connectors,” with “the world’s largest overpass, the Natuurbrug Zanderif Cariloo” found in the Netherlands (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 71). This overpass stretches over half a mile and crosses over a highway, a railroad, and a sports complex. In India in 2019, a highway was constructed through a tiger reserve and the entire

road itself was elevated and set on concrete pillars to allow for uninterrupted movement by the animals. However, not all crossing structures are created equal. While most overpasses are designed to cater to one species in particular, others, such as the Liberty Canyon Overpass in California, sometimes serve an entire ecosystem. The Liberty Canyon is made up of “microclimatic moments,” small areas designed for certain species that make up the whole landscape of the overpass (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 83). Additionally, Yellowstone to Yukon, or Y2Y, is a project that aims to create a connected habitat that results in a safe and continuous corridor along the spine of the Rockies through which animals would be able to travel unencumbered. This corridor would support multiple species and various migratory routes.

BENEFITS OF CROSSING STRUCTURES

Reconnecting habitats through crossing structures provides more benefits than just a reduction in wildlife-vehicle collisions (WVCs). In Wisconsin, reintroducing wolves culled the local deer population and saved nearly \$11 million annually. A study in the northeast found that reintroducing cougars could “prevent 700,000 deer-vehicle collisions and 155 driver deaths over thirty years” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 86). Fiscal benefits are not the only reason to consider putting the natural world back together. Just as it is good for mental health to be outside and experience the outdoors, it is good to be able to experience wildlife. A survey of people in Minnesota “found that every crushed turtle cost the state around \$3,000 in ‘passive-use value’ – econospeak for how much the public liked having turtles around” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 100). In Florida, biologist Matthew Aresco developed a design, known as an EcoPassage, to get turtles and other herps across a busy road that bisected Lake Jackson. This design consisted of a “chest-high concrete wall punctuated by four box culverts,” and was used by a range of animals, from turtles to snakes to alligators (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 104). In the western United States, culverts are being replaced or removed altogether to facilitate salmon migrations that have been disrupted due to their construction. This project, however, is benefiting more than just the salmon. There are indigenous tribes in those areas that depend on the salmon for the livelihood and their culture, and culverts had, purposefully or not, affected the daily lives of these people. The

removal and improvement of them would restore that heritage, thus serving as an act of environmental justice as well as ecological restoration. In Washington, the Culverts Case, a lawsuit brought against the state by several indigenous tribes, is aiming to restore or remove all culverts within the state. However, the state has aimed at transforming these culverts into crossings for terrestrial animals as well. By adding simple features such as elevated ledges as walkways, the state is “averting collisions and recouping some costs” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 208).

RELATION TO ALLIGATORS

The apex predator of the Louisiana habitat is the American alligator. Until 1987, the population of alligators was critically low, and the alligator was considered an endangered species. In the past 50 years, the Louisiana population has grown from less than 100,000 to over 2 million, with higher concentrations in the coastal regions of the state. However, less than 15% of wild alligators reach five feet in length, indicating that most do not reach five years of age. The reduction in length and age is a crucial statistic because at these stages in their development, alligators are susceptible to predators and cannot reproduce (Louisiana Department of Wildlife and Fisheries). Most of Louisiana’s alligator population is located within the southern marshes of the state closer to the coastline, but land loss and coastal erosion are pushing the alligator population north. This migration will increase the existing population within the Maurepas Swamp area and apply further stress to the disconnected habitat. In addition, people will also have to migrate north to land that is less threatened, which will create a need for expanded cities and more infrastructure development (Lustgarden, 2024). This study is timely and relevant, with the potential to serve as a foundation for future road projects.

Most alligators found in the wild in Louisiana were raised by state-licensed farmers and released once they reach a certain age. Once released, these young alligators must establish their territory and develop their home range, otherwise known as the area within which an animal interacts with the environment to meet its survival needs, which will determine their daily movements and routine. When looking at factors that determine movement among alligators, it was found that juveniles tend to move more than adults as

well as males more than females. The home range of adult female alligators is anywhere between less than half a square mile to one full square mile. On the other hand, the home range of male alligators was found to range from about 0.7 square miles to 20 square miles, with the longest travel distance recorded at 50 miles in a day (Lance, Valentine A., et al, 2011). These movements are restricted due to the construction of roads and highways through Louisiana wetlands and the subsequent creation of disconnected habitat fragments. Thus, alligators are forced to traverse roads to meet their survival needs and often become the victims of WVCs, affecting the alligator population in Louisiana.

Like alligators in size and slow breeding habits, large predatory cats can be used as a comparison species. Such animals are more affected by roads and infrastructure “because their immense territories are easily dissected ... [and] their small, slow-growing populations can’t withstand many collisions” (Goldfarb, 2023, p. 85). The same can be assumed for the American Alligator. There tends to be higher cases of WVCs involving alligators during warmer months because the asphalt on roads absorbs solar radiation and retains that heat, attracting alligators looking to regulate their body temperature. In addition, alligators tend to go into a form of hibernation in the winter, creating burrows in the ground in which they stay during the colder months. These collisions are the result of roads and highways that were built catering to people and disregarding the existing landscapes and habitats that they cut through.

TECHNOLOGY

Geospatial technology is being used to directly monitor wildlife movements. By attaching radio collars to the animal, scientists can get “approximate movement paths ... and home ranges” (Morse, 2021, par. 34). This helps scientists better understand the animals and identify areas of greater importance to the survival of the species they monitor. VHF radio telemetry and in-water acoustic receivers are two prominent methods for recording movements of crocodylian species. These species are “large-sized mobile aquatic predators frequently inhabiting remote areas” (Fujisaki et al, 2014). Radio transmitters have been used to record daily and weekly movements in studies to determine alligator home ranges in marsh habitats. The drawback of this method is that it is difficult to monitor

“movements of highly mobile species for more extended periods in remote areas” (Fujisaki et al, 2014). GPS and satellite telemetry are also alternative methods, although satellite telemetry has lower costs and increased battery longevity compared to GPS telemetry, which is more advantageous for monitoring movements in remote areas.

FUNDING AND POLICY

The National Environmental Policy Act, NEPA, is a federal process that is designed to change this norm and reduce the ecological impact of roads and road construction. However, over 90% of transportation projects in the United States are determined by state transportation departments to have little or no impacts. Thus, they are classified as categorical exclusions and therefore are not required to be reviewed by an outside agency using the NEPA process (US EPA, OP, 2013). The Biden Administration in the United States has pledged \$10.1 billion to Louisiana through the Infrastructure Bill, with \$3.84 billion of that total allotted for roads, bridges, and safety. Some of this funding could be allocated to crossing structures and infrastructure that aims to reduce WVCs and reconnect habitats.

SUMMARY

In the modern world, roads are essential to civilization. Without them, cities and people would be isolated, and the framework of society would crumble. However, the current infrastructure is unsustainable for the continued survival of genetic biodiversity within the ecosystems of the world. Essential migrations are halted, territories are restricted, and animal access to food, water, and potential mates is inhibited by roads and the vehicles that utilize them. Crossing structures are a viable solution to this ever-growing problem. Through these structures as well as supplemental design elements such as wildlife fencing and illuminated signage, WVCs have been proven to be reduced and once-fragmented habitats have been reconnected, restoring the ecological corridors historically found in those regions.

METHODS

To design a crossing structure that will serve to re-establish ecological corridors and reduce wildlife collisions within the 15-mile stretch of I-10 between Sorrento and LaPlace,

the impact of I-10 on the natural habitats it cuts through must be identified and described. To do so, a series of steps have been completed and additional supporting elements for project awareness have been developed.

WILDLIFE-VEHICLE COLLISION INVENTORY

Along Interstate 10 in both the east and westbound lanes, wildlife hit by cars were located, photographed, and recorded. An inventory sheet was created to gather specific data regarding the roadkill and to ensure that no occurrence was duplicated.

ROADKILL INVENTORY

Record ID: _____

Date and Time: _____

GPS Coordinates: _____

East or West – bound? _____

Type of Animal: _____

Size of Animal: _____

Nearby Natural Features: _____

Cars after 30 sec? _____

Cars after 60 sec? _____

Photograph? YES NO

NOTES:

Image 1 | A copy of the roadkill inventory data sheet.

Four inventories were conducted over a ten-month span and 121 incidents were recorded. The inventory began at Exit 187 in Sorrento, LA, and ended at the beginning of the Spencer Chauvin Memorial Bridge in LaPlace, LA. This task was conducted by driving down I-10

along the shoulder and pulling over at each occurrence of roadkill. Using the inventory sheet listed above, the incidents were recorded and photographed. It should be noted that not every animal was recorded due to:

- An inability to pull over at the time of sighting because of dangerous road conditions, normally too much road traffic.
- Only animals on the larger right-roadside shoulder were recorded, not the animals along the left-roadside median.

Therefore, the total number of incidents recorded is not a true reflection of the total number of incidents that occur.

The data from the roadkill inventories was compiled into an excel spreadsheet that was used to summarize specific information regarding the incidents such as which lane, east or west, was the most deadly and which species were among the top killed.

Record Number	Date	Time	Latitude	Longitude	East or West	Type of Animal	Size of Animal INCHES	Nearby Natural Features	Cars after 30 seconds	Cars after 60 seconds	Photograph	Notes
1	3/28/2024	15:41	30.28379	-80.84422		Armadillo	20	Wooded	28	28		Relatively fresh, still pink, smelly
2	3/28/2024	10:09	30.19639	-80.52987		Raccoon	30	Heavily wooded median, wooded shoulder	14	45		Almost completely flattened, not very smelly, mummified
3	3/28/2024	10:20	30.19611	-80.50778		Raccoon	20	Heavily wooded median, wooded shoulder	14	17		Mummified, no smell, almost flat
4	3/28/2024	10:24	30.19611	-80.50956		Undentifiable	10	Heavily wooded median, wooded shoulder	10	35		Mummified, no smell, flat
5	3/28/2024	10:34	30.17472	-80.81444		Undentifiable	20	Heavily wooded median, wooded shoulder	10	25		Smelly, drying flesh
6	3/28/2024	10:47	30.18487	-80.81687		Armadillo	12	Wooded and hilly shoulder	25	57		Sun bleached, locals destroyed
7	3/28/2024	10:51	30.18487	-80.81522		Turtle	12	Wooded and hilly shoulder	30	34		Shed scattered
8	3/28/2024	10:55	30.18487	-80.80833		Turtle	12	Wooded hilly shoulder, creek	36	29		Sun bleached, scattered shell
9	3/28/2024	11:00	30.18487	-80.80833		Choi	12	Wooded and hilly shoulder, creek	23	40		Fresh kill, magpie right before
10	3/28/2024	11:04	30.18487	-80.80833		Undentifiable	12	Wooded hilly shoulder, creek	30	43		Small, crushed, smelly, still bloody
11	3/28/2024	11:12	30.18278	-80.80278		Undentifiable	18	Woody part shoulder	15	23		Leg cannot be seen, 20 yds east of hill, old kill, bones bleached, no smell, mummified
12	3/28/2024	11:50	30.19295	-80.81989		Alligator	20	Swamp, woods, trees, flat land	19	37		Remains scattered about 15 ft, bones bleached, been dead for a while, totally ripped apart
13	3/28/2024	11:29	30.14844	-80.78111		FrogToad	20	Swamp, trees, flat land	6	18		Fresh
14	3/28/2024	11:36	30.14811	-80.78200		Undentifiable	10	Swamp	13	15		Old, mummified, sun bleached
15	3/28/2024	11:43	30.14222	-80.79578		Deer	20	Swamp, woods	20	30		Smelly, flat, absolutely crushed and shattered, body parts strewn along shoulder
16	3/28/2024	11:50	30.13972	-80.74844		Mania	20	Swamp, woods	23	35		Fresh, flesh is red/pink, bloody, doesn't smell yet
17	3/28/2024	11:57	30.13944	-80.73987		Raccoon	30	Swamp, woods	36	27		Old, sunbleached, mummified
18	3/28/2024	12:01	30.13944	-80.72111		Choi	10	Swamp, woods	15	30		Smelly
19	3/28/2024	12:07	30.12867	-80.70311		Undentifiable	10	Swamp, woods	11	22		Old, mummified
20	3/28/2024	12:14	30.12278	-80.67639		Alligator	30	Swamp, woods	18	34		In multiple pieces, been dead a while
21	3/28/2024	12:24	30.11611	-80.62987		Alligator	18	Swamp, woods	19	46		Been dead a while, bones are bleached
22	3/28/2024	12:25	30.11656	-80.60989		Alligator	42	Swamp, woods	13	30		Been dead a while, bones bleached, small
23	3/28/2024	12:36	30.11956	-80.59778		Choi	10	Swamp, woods	22	41		In road, flattened
24	3/28/2024	12:42	30.11444	-80.58444		Choi	12	Swamp, woods	13	27		Body parts strewn across shoulder
25	3/28/2024	12:46	30.11444	-80.58311		Undentifiable	20	Swamp, woods	23	33		Smelly
26	3/28/2024	12:52	30.11096	-80.56778		Undentifiable	26	Swamp, woods	13	26		Smelly
27	3/28/2024	12:55	30.10278	-80.55222		Undentifiable	30	Swamp, woods	18	27		Crushed
28	3/28/2024	13:06	30.09687	-80.47056		Undentifiable	36	Wooded shoulder with open field	18	31		Smelly, body parts strewn across shoulder
29	3/28/2024	13:50	30.11611	-80.59200		Deer	26	Swamp, woods	12	29		Squeezed and flat, smelly
30	3/28/2024	13:56	30.11444	-80.58111		Deer	42	Swamp, bays, creek	16	27		Smelly, flattened
31	3/28/2024	16:03	30.11639	-80.60189		Undentifiable	20	Swamp, woods	24	41		Squeezed, no smell
32	3/28/2024	16:08	30.11644	-80.60956		Choi	10	Swamp, woods	32	43		Smelly
33	3/28/2024	16:13	30.11178	-80.61333		Opossum	10	Swamp, woods	8	17		Very flat, sunbleached
34	3/28/2024	16:15	30.11178	-80.61333		Choi	10	Swamp, woods	13	26		Very flat, no smell
35	3/28/2024	16:20	30.11778	-80.61887		Turtle	18	Swamp, woods	28	41		Relatively fresh
36	3/28/2024	16:23	30.12144	-80.61306		Raccoon	20	Swamp, woods	13	38		Squeezed, sunbleached
37	3/28/2024	16:41	30.12133	-80.60078		Raccoon	30	Swamp, woods	16	21		Flat, sunbleached
38	3/28/2024	16:40	30.12056	-80.70687		Rabbit	18	Swamp, woods	23	39		Fresh, smelly, flesh still red
39	3/28/2024	16:47	30.12122	-80.70444		Undentifiable	12	Swamp, woods	4	16		Smashed, sunbleached
40	3/28/2024	16:56	30.14811	-80.74222		Choi	10	Swamp, woods	30	39		Fresh, maybe white, lot of legs
41	3/28/2024	17:05	30.16	-80.62361		Choi	12	Swamp, woods	28	39		Smelly
42	3/28/2024	17:09	30.16078	-80.59722		Raccoon	18	Swamp, woods	10	26		Flat, sunbleached, smelly
43	3/28/2024	17:20	30.13187	-80.9125		Raccoon	30	Heavily wooded median, wooded shoulder	6	23		Very fresh, probably this morning
44	4/7/2024	12:04	30.19639	-80.82222		Undentifiable	18	Heavily wooded shoulder	13	27		1
45	4/7/2024	12:08	30.19639	-80.81944		Snake	18	Heavily wooded shoulder	4	20		1
46	4/7/2024	12:16	30.19556	-80.78889		Armadillo	20	Swamp, creek, woods	18	26		1
47	4/7/2024	12:36	30.19556	-80.78889		FrogToad	13	Swamp, creek, woods	18	26		1
48	4/7/2024	12:36	30.19556	-80.78889		Undentifiable	18	Swamp, creek, woods	18	26		1
49	4/7/2024	12:27	30.18611	-80.78822		Snake	12	Swamp, woods	10	18		1
50	4/7/2024	12:38	30.18633	-80.79222		Raccoon	18	Swamp, woods	18	29		1
51	4/7/2024	12:47	30.12889	-80.71883		Armadillo	27	Woody, river, swamp	10	29		1
52	4/7/2024	12:55	30.12867	-80.69887		Deer	20	Swamp, woods	19	29		1
53	4/7/2024	13:04	30.1225	-80.67361		Undentifiable	22	Swamp, woods	15	28		1
54	4/7/2024	13:05	30.11811	-80.6025		Raccoon	20	Swamp, woods	25	38		1
55	4/7/2024	13:23	30.11678	-80.61944		Swapping Turtle	25	Swamp, woods	15	23		1
56	4/7/2024	14:00	30.11527	-80.60956		Choi	18	Swamp, woods	20	35		1
57	4/7/2024	14:06	30.11687	-80.61444		Alligator	42	Swamp, woods	10	29		1
58	10/15/2024	3:25	30.19544	-80.79644		Raccoon	24	Swamp, shoulder	8	17		1
59	10/15/2024	3:31	30.19567	-80.79572		Undentifiable	12	Swamp, wooded shoulder	16	19		1
60	10/15/2024	14:01	30.14472	-80.73222		Raccoon	22	Swamp, wooded shoulder	14	24		1
61	10/15/2024	14:41	30.14444	-80.7626		Undentifiable	14	Swamp, wooded shoulder	8	14		1

Image 7 | Screenshot of the Excel Master File containing all information from the roadkill inventories.

Image 8 | Graph depicting roadkill incidents by lane direction on Interstate 10.

Image 9 | Graph depicting roadkill incident frequencies by type of animal.

MAPPING AND SITE SELECTION

Maps were produced using GPS coordinates from the inventory process to support the site selection. The GPS coordinates were converted from degrees minutes seconds to decimal degrees and then upload to ArcGIS as a new feature class. To establish collision “hot spots”, a kernel density was applied to this feature class.

Image 10 | Roadkill incident density map. Found in orange are the individual roadkill incidents while the blue-green gradient is depicting incident density.

This map acted as a visualization of the WVCs and helped to identify the most effective and potentially successful locations for wildlife crossing structures that will result in the highest reduction in collisions. The largest hot spot is found on the far right and is the site that will be used for the purposes of this design. In addition, minor interventions such as wildlife fencing and light and sound emitters are suggested to be placed in areas where WVCs occur but that are not suitable for crossing structures. These interventions serve to reduce wildlife contact with the road.

SITE HISTORY AND ANALYSIS

After reviewing historical imagery of the site provided by the Louisiana Department of Transportation, it was concluded that the site today is damaged. There is a lack of tree canopy since the trees in the area are either dead or dying. The water surrounding the mouths of the canal is brown and has an oily shine on the surface due to motor oil runoff and potential contamination from the refineries to the south of the site. There are canals that run directly from the Marathon and Atlantic Alumina refineries into the site.

Additionally, the Atlantic Alumina refinery is currently under investigation for compliance with environmental codes. There is a bright green algal bloom occurring in the water as well which can lead to a reduction in the oxygen levels in the water, resulting in wildlife deaths.

Image 11 | Historical imagery of the site from October 7, 1971. Imagery provided by the Louisiana Department of

Image 12 | Satellite imagery of the site today showing runoff canals from the refineries directly into the site.

Image 13 | Existing conditions of the site. Mouth of the canal running into four 3-ft wide concrete culverts that run under the interstate to the other side.

Image 14-16 | Existing conditions of the site. Oil sheen on the water, brown water, and algal bloom.

CASE STUDY

The largest hotspot chosen from the mappings was the site selected to be used as a case study. This case study is intended to serve as a model for future related projects. The design consists of a wildlife crossing structure, more specifically an underpass, and an interactive museum and trail that will include information about the project, serving as an educational experience with which the public can interact. Information included in the exhibit will include but is not limited to: description and examples of ecological connectivity, wildlife corridors, and habitat fragmentation, local context to the site, the

process of conducting roadkill inventories and why they are significant, the native plant communities, the wildlife served through the construction of the underpass, and so on.

CONCEPTUAL STUDIES

A series of conceptual studies were conducted to devise an organic and naturalistic design for the shape and flow of the canal that reflected the values of the project. These studies were conducted using water and ink as well as water and sediment. For the water and ink studies, ink drops were placed into a container of water and paper was placed onto the surface of the mixture.

Image 17-21 | Water and ink conceptual studies.

For the water and sediment studies, sediment was collected and mixed into a container of water. This mixture was then repeatedly spilled out onto various pieces of paper. In some instances, alligator scales were placed on the paper to act as barriers to the movement of water and to allow the sediment to pool and gather in certain areas.

Image 22-24 | Water and sediment conceptual studies.

Image 25-26 | Water and sediment conceptual studies utilizing alligator

The results of these two studies were then put into Adobe Photoshop and were overlaid to find moments of density, potential pathways, and gaps in the overlays.

Image 27 | Water and ink conceptual study overlay.

Image 28 | Water and ink conceptual study overlay.

Image 29 | Water and sediment conceptual study overlay.

These overlays were then abstracted and placed into the general layout of the canal shape. With the basic form determined, the overlays were woven into the tessellation-like design of an alligator's back to ground the design into the values of the project.

Image 30 | Conceptual study exploring the possible abstraction of the water studies into the tessellation-like design of an alligator's back.

Image 31-33 | Conceptual studies exploring the possible abstraction of the water studies into the tessellation-like design of an alligator's back.

SOFTWARE

The software used throughout this process included: ArcGIS Pro, Rhino 3DS, Lumion, Adobe Illustrator, Adobe Photoshop, and Microsoft Excel.

RESULTS

FINAL DESIGN

The design intervention selected to remediate the site and reduce WVCs in the area is a wildlife crossing in the form of an underpass. To create the underpass, the interstate has been raised to a maximum height of 20 feet and the canal beneath has been day lit and restored. The portion of interstate rising to the 20-foot maximum runs for 400 feet on either side of the flat elevated portion which spans 100 feet. The grade of the road does not exceed 3%. The bridge is supported by 20-inch-thick concrete pylons that abut 28-inch-thick concrete beams. The supports are spaced 40 feet on center. The underpass itself spans a width of 333 feet and stretches a length of 206 feet from the south end to the north. The openness ratio of this underpass is 32.3. This number was found by multiplying the

height and width of the underpass and dividing that number by the length: (20 ft x 333 ft) / 206 ft = 32.3.

The restoration of the canal is achieved by exposing the water, naturalizing the bank, expanding the width and increasing the depth of the canal, and revitalizing the native plants found throughout. The plant palette features all native plants, focusing on remediation plants on the southern end of the canal intended to remove pollutants from the soil and water. The trees featured in this design are: Bald Cypress | *Taxodium distichum*, Water Oak | *Quercus nigra*, Cherrybark Oak | *Quercus pagoda*, Live Oak | *Quercus virginiana*, American Sycamore | *Platanus occidentalis*, Red Maple | *Acer rubrum*, Southern Magnolia | *Magnolia grandiflora*, American Beech | *Fagus grandifolia*, Swamp Dogwood | *Cornus foemina*, River Birch | *Betula nigra*. The shrubs featured in this design are: Dwarf Palmetto | *Sabal minor*, Buttonbush | *Cephalanthus occidentalis*, Swamp Milkweed | *Asclepias incarnata*, Swamp Rose Mallow | *Hibiscus moscheutos*, Louisiana Iris | *Iris hexagona*. The remediation plants featured in this design are: Smooth Cordgrass | *Spartina alterniflora*, Common Duckweed | *Lemna minor*, Bulrush | *Typha latifolia*, Soft Rush | *Juncus effusus*, Grassleaf Rush | *Juncus marginatus*.

This underpass includes a raised trail system and an immersive museum through which the trail runs. This museum is intended to serve as a public engagement initiative that will spread awareness about the importance of ecological connectivity and wildlife corridors and how modern infrastructure often degrades both, resulting in habitat fragmentation.

The trail itself is a raised platform trail coming to a maximum height of 20 feet and is constructed out of a patinaed core-ten steel frame and supports and an accompanying patinaed core-ten steel grated flooring. The trail has a width of 12 feet, the same as the width of the museum, to ensure a seamless flow between trail and museum. The museum is encased in the same patinaed core-ten steel frame as the trail but features a design inspired by the branching patterns of trees. It is an almost all-glass building to allow continuous views out into the landscape and to immerse the user in the canopy of the surrounding trees. The floor features a glass panel that runs from end to end to allow users

to view the forest floor and any wildlife that may be passing through. The roof of the museum features a corrugated steel topping with a light filter beneath it on the interior of the museum. This filter is also inspired by the branching patterns of trees and is intended to filter out the harsh, direct sunlight to allow for a softer experience.

Image 34 | Exit ramp off Interstate 10 to parking area for raised forest walk and museum experience.

Image 35 | Forest walk entrance featuring geographical marker and textured wildlife fence. Artwork by Leah Marchand and Layne Roland, used with permission.

Image 36 | Museum interior featuring exterior branch wrap, light filter, and glass floor.

Image 37 | Raised forest walk featuring native plants and steel structure.

Image 38 | View of daylit canal.

Image 39 | View of daylit canal within the context of the interstate underpass.

Image 40 | Perspective of underpass featuring wildlife corridors and the potential wildlife users of the site.

Image 41 | View of wildlife corridor for aquatic animals such as turtles, alligators, frogs, river otters, etc.

Image 42 | View of wildlife corridor for terrestrial animals such as deer, raccoons, coyotes, armadillos, etc.

Image 43 | Section perspective featuring plant palette, canal depth, and soil composition.

LOCAL ARTIST PARTNERSHIPS

This design features artwork by two local artists, Leah Marchand and Layne Roland. Born in New Orleans and raised in Baton Rouge, Leah Marchand finds inspiration for her art through her connections. Connections to her past, her home, and the things she loves. The works used in this project are from the artist's Leather Map Series. According to her website, the "Louisiana Leather series is a fresh take on the old land grant maps of the Mississippi River and is a unique way to celebrate the beautiful Louisiana swamps and Gulf Coast". The two pieces Leah provided for this project feature maps of Louisiana cities, one of New Orleans and one of Baton Rouge, built into the tessellation-like scale design on the back of an alligator. Her artwork serves as a location marker at both entrances to the raised forest walk. The map of New Orleans is found at the entrance to the forest walk on the west-bound side of I-10 with New Orleans behind it while the map of Baton Rouge is found at the entrance to the forest walk on the east-bound side of I-10 with Baton Rouge behind it. These two maps are intended to ground the user and provide some local context, telling them where they are within the state.

Image 44 | Map of New Orleans embedded into the tessellation-like scale design of the back of an alligator. This piece is from the artist's Leather Map Series. Artwork by Leah Marchand, used with permission.

Image 45 | Map of Baton Rouge embedded into the tessellation-like scale design of the back of an alligator. This piece is from the artist's Leather Map Series. Artwork by Leah Marchand, used with permission.

Image 46 | Leah Marchand.

As a Louisiana native, Layne Roland has a passion for the outdoors and an endless fascination for the diverse beauty and entangled rhythms of the natural world. Layne's creative process and art works are inspired by the complexities of nature and immersing herself within natural ecosystems. Through an organic and intuitive process, she hand-builds biomorphic forms that are both sculptural and functional. By engaging with Layne's work, people can experience a greater sense of intrigue and a deeper connection with nature. Layne donated original artwork to this project. She created a series of glazed ceramic tiles on which she pressed the backs of alligator scales to give a unique texture. These tiles are intended to serve as the texture for the wildlife fence that faces the parking area for the raised forest walk and museum experience.

Image 47 | Original glazed ceramic tiles featuring the texture of alligator scales. Artwork by Layne Roland, used with permission.

Image 48 | Selected tiles for use in design project. Artwork by Layne Roland, used with permission.

Image 49 | Layne Roland and her son.

NEXT STEPS

GALLERY EXHIBITION

As a supportive element and public awareness and engagement initiative, a photographic exhibition highlighting the WVCs along I-10 will be curated. This exhibition will consist of the photographs taken during the inventory stage and is intended to be innovative, bold, and provocative, focusing on the severe state of the environment and the direction in which it is headed. Also included in the exhibition will be the designs for the crossing structure to show that solutions to this problem do exist. The goal of this exhibition is to start a conversation that realizes the de-sensitivity towards roadkill and garners support for efforts that aim to reduce it.

LOUISIANA DEPARTMENT OF TRANSPORTATION PARTNERSHIPS

To bring further relevance and support to this project, a partnership with the Louisiana Department of Transportation will be explored. The goal of this partnership is to create a statewide roadkill inventory system that catalogs roadkill across the state on various roads. This inventory system will be able to discern which roads throughout the state of Louisiana are the most dangerous to wildlife and can inform design decisions and interventions that

can serve to reduce these WVCs. Additionally, a statewide roadkill inventory system will help to provide a better understanding of wildlife populations within the state and how they fluctuate related to WVCs. Understanding the wildlife populations will allow the design team to determine potential wildlife corridors throughout the state that have either been lost or do not currently exist. This information will better inform future locations for wildlife crossings across the state.

COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

More partnerships with local artists will be explored to further engage the community and spread awareness of this work. Other partnerships will be explored, such as those with local organizations that conduct similar or related research or work regarding wildlife and ecological connectivity within the state. Once these partnerships have been solidified, in-person events could begin to be held where the community can come out and learn about the topic, the issues and concerns, the possible solutions, and so on. Local vendors can set up booths and sell their merchandise alongside food vendors that are selling local dishes that potentially include relevant animal species. Such events would be considered miniature ecological fairs or festivals and would be an informal, fun and collaborative way to engage the community and spread awareness.

RESEARCH PARTNERSHIPS AND GRANTS

Research institutions that provide grant money for research will be contacted and applications will be sent out with the hopes of receiving funding to further this project and its outreach initiatives. Grant money would support soil and water quality testing, expenses related to the gallery exhibition, and expenses related to the community engagement initiatives. Additionally, research partnerships with local or regional groups will be explored to improve the scientific research portion of the project and provide a richer foundation on which this project can build.

CONCLUSION

Interstate 10 between Sorrento and LaPlace, Louisiana, is a dangerous 15 mile stretch for the wildlife who interact with it. After a series of four roadkill inventories conducted over a

10-month period from March to December of 2024, 121 roadkill incidents were recorded and over 16 animal species were affected. These inventories shed light on a deeper problem: the lack of access wildlife has to its own habitat because of human expansion and uninformed infrastructure development. However, the solution seems simple: wildlife crossing structures. Through the design development of a wildlife crossing structure underpass that cuts underneath I-10, ecological connectivity was restored and a wildlife corridor was created. This underpass features a native plant palette that will boost ecological function and remediate any damage to the area by pollutants from road and refinery runoff. The design incorporates a raised forest walk and museum experience that immerses users, both local and touring alike, in a native Louisiana landscape and allows them to experience firsthand all that a wildlife crossing structure can do. Through this project, the community is engaged, and awareness of such issues is raised that could potentially lead to further change and involvement. It is through this type of research and design that change is achieved, and work can be done to pave the way for a better tomorrow.

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